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HEALTH MANAGEMENT:
REALIGNING SYSTEMS,
CONTEXTS AND PLAYERS

ABSTRACT BOOK

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SDGs and Green Deal as players in health care sector transformation in the context of climate change

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Environmental, economic and social impacts influence the sustainability pathway of all health care systems. Transformation of health sector is a necessary process to emphasize sustainability. Health care systems should realign themselves and work on sustainability and better adaptation to the changing environment. The mission of the health sector is protecting human health, but unfortunately, it has also a major contribution to the climate change process. Health care sector's climate footprint is equivalent to 4.4% of global net emissions, equivalent to the annual greenhouse gas emissions from more than 500 coal-fired power plants.

Health care's climate footprint sources are numerous. During the process of health care delivering, health care systems also produce emissions of greenhouse gases, both directly and indirectly. Reduction of these emissions should be implemented at national or regional levels. According to the data available, emissions emanating directly from health care facilities and vehicles owned by health care systems make about 17%, indirect emissions from purchased energy sources such as electricity, steam, cooling, and heating comprise another 12%, and 71% represent the majority of emissions, primarily derived from the health care supply chain through the production, transport, and disposal of goods and services, such as pharmaceuticals and other chemicals, food and agricultural products, medical devices, hospital equipment, and instruments (HCWH&Arup 2019).

The health care sector should take accountability for its climate footprint and react to the rising climate change emergency not only by treating patients, but also by fundamentally reducing its own emissions through taking informed decisions. Health care climate action is aligned with the ambition of the Paris Agreement to achieve net zero emissions by 2050 or even earlier. Health care sector must undertake this effort by using Sustainable Development Goals and Green Deal as major arguments.

Climate change is a serious challenge for health sector. Climate impacts increase burden of different disease, morbidity and mortality on one side, but also press the health service provision and increase emission and footprint, on the other side. Decarbonization strategies in the health care sector should take into account that people in low income countries are living without sufficient health care. Future research has to investigate the connection between the health carbon footprint, health care performance and health outcome (Pichler 2019). What is needed hereof is better understanding of the permeation a health care and climate change, analysis of health care emissions in future, investigation of the supply chain of health sector and its climate impact, health and economic costs, as well as the benefits analysis of transition to climate-smart healthcare. All of the above require further research.

Since Green Deal aims at an inclusive transition to help improve people's well-being and secure a healthy planet for generations to come, it is also important to improve Health care organizations. Transformation should follow the roadmap towards SDGs, EU Green Deal, and other useful agreements in mitigating the climate change and better adaptation of the health systems to new circumstances. Health managers should use SDGs and Green Deal as "players" to better organize and lead health systems to sustainability.